

VARIOUS TRENDS ABOUT RESERVATION AND SOME REMEDIES FOR ITS EFFECTIVE IMPLEMENTATION

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Abstract-

This research study focuses on the injustice happened and happening with SC/ST in Maharashtra. Due to the upper class ruling people; the survey which they do especially BPL is been always faulty therefore landlord, rich, big politicians get the advantage of Govt. Schemes whereas the SC/ST families those who are working on their farm, they themselves are unemployed and landless; don't have BPL card. So they are not eligible so as to get advantages of Govt. Schemes to improve their life style and standard. Implementation of Reservation Policy is also not proper; many organizations like CASTTRIBE take lead for fulfilling the backlog in govt. sectors. But, the people sitting in the chair are not showing their interest and any kind of action. The organization representatives are given only promises and deadline always been extended with this or that reason. How can these backward class people will be brought into the main flow of the society; is a matter of a research but that research also will remain on paper when this kind of mentality of people will be there. It's a high time, for govt. to put efforts seriously as we have completed 61 years of independence. Will these people get justice? When? How?

Introduction:

Dictionary meaning of definition- Oxford English Dictionary, Vol- 11-1972 page. 2506- The Action or Fact Reserving (for oneself or another) some rights, power privilege etc. is reservation.

Many of the philosopher's writer's have defined the term reservation as a REPRESENTATION. India is a country known for many good things and one bad thing i.e. caste-system. Due to caste-system India is behind in many things compare to all other countries of the world. Caste plays a vital role in Indian context. A person is not known by his talent but at initial stage he is known by his caste. Almost from last 60 years, the backward categories like SC/ST/ are getting reservations. Even today, one can easily identify that category of people either by their appearance or social-economical status. Of course, reservation has lifted many life but 70% people are even today living the life as they were. Many of the great schemes and policies of the govt. have not reached to them. When central/state govt. made survey of Below Poverty Level (BPL); many of the poor and need are out of the list and rich upper classes are included in it. So rich are getting the benefits of poor people that's why the condition of backward classes is not improved as it should. The govt. operating system is in hands of upper caste people and even today their mentality is of Manu.

Five stages of Reservation in India:-

1. Manusmriti.
2. British time.
3. Rajyeshri Shahu Maharaj.
4. Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar.
5. Indian Constitution

In all these stages reservation was and is based on 'CASTE'. Upper caste people should help others for their progress and they should feel backward should come at our par. It is because progress of the country depends upon the progress of each individual. Many of people have different feelings about reservation and these feeling have turned into various trends of about reservation.

A) Reservation and Quality:-

For the growth & the development of any individual & community background is very important. The communities which are far from the main-stream will not give essence background for their children. Due to their economical status they might not send

their children to school or they will take their children out from the school and will seek an job for them before 18 years. The students those who are getting everything as per their demand will definitely show their good performance in the form of percentage. These students can get admission in known institutions like I.I.T, IIMS, MEDICAL AND ENGINEERING whereas without reservation backward class students will feel it as a dream. Reservation is at the entry level, once they are in all set criteria is same to all – like passing % required, syllabus, question paper, assessment. There is no compromise with the quality. As Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar said, ‘Given an opportunity is a merit’. Marks on paper and talent are two different things. If, provided the equal background, backward class students will not be behind. So there will not be a question of lower quality doctor, engineer or scientist. Once he gets track; he reaches to destination. With intention of social justice, these people should be given reservation in all sectors of life to prove their quality, capacity and capability. And the best examples of it’s result are the Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar, Dr. Bhalchandra Mungekar, Ex-member of Planning Commission, GOI, Dr. Sukhdev Thorat, Chairman-U.G.C., Dr. Narendra Jadhav, Member of Planning Commission, GOI.. Few of the people are trying to oppose reservation by raising the issue of quality which is baseless.

B) Reservation and Caste-system:

This is another trend about reservation that reservation is strengthening caste-system. The people having such feelings should keep one thing in mind that caste-system and casteism in India was in existence before the policy of reservation. In continuation to it these liars are saying our Identity should be only Indian. On surface any Indian can support their opinion. But, few questions come in my mind – Will caste-system collapse totally if reservation is withdrawn? One thing I would like to make very clear that the people having such opinion are objecting caste by saying we don’t want dividation among us but their objection/opposition is not for caste and it is only for reservation. Caste-system is the base of Indian society and at no time it will vanish. The students from upper castes; are made to stand in front of various institutions holding various slogans in their hand. Like, WE ALL ARE EQUAL, WE HATE RESERVATION, and STOP RESERVATION and so on.

These immature groups of students have had any idea of reservation. They don't have the sense of what they are doing? These upper caste people should keep one thing in mind that your fore father's are the pioneer of caste-system/casteism and today you are speaking about the system with the intention to vanish reservation and not the caste-system and casteism.

C) OBC should have Cream-layer:

More than 6000 castes India are getting 50 seats and few upper castes getting 50 seats. Backward classes population is 85% of the total population and are getting only 50% seats whereas 15% upper castes are getting 50% seats. These 50% seats for open category are also reserved for them so there is no point talking about another 50% seats which are only kept for backward classes. The group of people/community who ever have not seen the cream, where is the question of getting the layer's of cream? In one judgment Supreme Court has said that there is no reservation on caste base in any of the country on the world. Caste-system is only in India and not at rest part of the world. From 16th Nov 1992, SC has put cream-layer criteria for OBC which is unconstitutional. Central Govt. had put 2.5 lacs annual income limit for OBC so as to get the benefit of reservation. 2.5 lac is the annual income of a lower middle class family and for their further prospectus and growth they will not be given the benefits of reservation, saying grass-root level people should get the benefit. When learned, knowledgeable people will not get the benefit of reservation after crossing the certain limit of income then they will back to the policy and result will be the policy will not reach to the poor. At the same there are poor people in upper castes; so as to get them the benefits of 50% open seats are there. The criteria of cream-layer should be put or made applicable for upper castes as there is also some % of poor people who only can give the benefit of open seats.

D) Reservation on Economic Status:

This is a very hot trend to be discussed- The poor from upper castes also should get some reservation. This is a new demand of certain category of people. But, demander should keep one thing in their mind that Reservation policy is not the polity of 'Garibi

Hatav'. In countries like America, England, Australia, Canada and Malaysia reservation is given to BLACK and they call reservation as "AFFIRMATIVE ACTION OR COMPENSATORY PRIVILEGE OR PROTECTIVE DISCRIMINATION". These benefits they are getting on race--- and not on their economical status. Nowhere in the world; reservation given on economical status, but it given on caste and race. In India backwards are known backward because of their caste and so reservation should only be given on basis of caste and not on any other condition.

- a) Reservation is representation:- the basic right of Indian Constitution Act 15 and 16 which one should not forget. 15 (c) says Reservation is only for socially and educationally backward classes and that is for SC/ST and there is not a provision for economical backward.
- b) According to 16 (c) the community which has not got /getting the representation should be given the reservation. Upper caste poor people will not get reservation because reservation is not for an INDIVIDUAL but it is or COMMUNITY. There communities representatives are more than enough in all sectors of life.
- c) Unconstitutionally, Narsaha Rao Govt. made some provision to give 10% reservation for upper castes poor from 25th Sept 1991 and that has been cancelled by SC.
- d) If Central/State Govt. is thinking to give reservation for economical backward class people then it will collapse on the day it starts. It is because the survey will not be done RELIABLE and the best example of it is the BPL SURVEY. Most of SC/ST are leaving the life of below poverty; but in Maharashtra and especially in my village all landlords, rich, politicians and well settled families have got this card to get benefit of various policies of Govt. ; if needed I will provide the list. **The unemployed families, dependant on others farm work, landless people's names are not there in the list of BPL, and this is very unfortunate. SC/ST landless people in Maharashtra are far away from getting the benefits of Govt.policies; to be mentioned SC/ST landless people**

- e) get a 3-5 acres piece of land from Govt. but many of the families are not eligible for getting the benefit of this scheme; it is because their names are not in the list of BPL. In this case, where and what is their fault? When Govt. is aware the BPL survey is 100% faulty then this condition should be removed so as to give benefit to SC/ST poor and landless family. (when person is unemployed, landless of course he works on daily basis income and his annual income is not more than 25 thousand and no savings in the bank for your more information 70% SC/ST have not seen the bank then there is not a question of having saving a/c and F.D. and future planning.)

This faulty survey had happened and will happen again and again because the system is in the hands of upper caste people and the reservation on basis of economical status will be farce. For getting some benefits people can change their income but they can't change their caste very easily. Backward classes are known for their castes and only on basis on it the reservation should be continued.

ROLE OF MEDIA:

Media plays a vital role in construction of society. Many channels, handle this tender issue by asking questions and telling people to SMS their opinion. Few of the people must be responding to them and data which they collect are generalized. Media should know many of backward classes are far away from I.T. So how can they respond to your question? Those who know are occupied with their work since morning to evening. Reservation is not fulfilled in Govt. and public sectors then how can they accommodate in private? Backlog is a good evidence of it.

SOME REMEDIES FOR EFFECTIVE IMPLEMENTATION OF RESERVATION:

1. Reserved category should be given free and compulsory education till graduation.
2. As per the increased population of the community; reservation should be increased.
3. Scholarships no. and funds need to increase.

4. Start- Reserve category care centre.
5. Reserve category people should be asked to give feedback about Govt. policies and implementing officer.
6. Ineffective implementing officer should be held responsible and it should be treated as unailable crime.
7. Workshops at Adivashi Pada/Dalit Vasti should be conducted.
8. Every year Central Govt. and State Govt. make provision of hundred and thousands of crore; really that money reaches to the poor and needy? If this would have been the truth, after 61 years of independence, the life style and standard of SC/ST would have not been only improved but they would have come at par of the upper class people. Then question arises- the provision made in budgets is just a show, to draw the votes of them and where that money goes?
9. Evaluation and assessment of Govt. funds should be done on time and beneficiary's name should be displayed on website with their name, address and contact no.

Conclusion:

In short, development of each community will help India to be Developed country. Even today India is a developing country, could be the reason of caste-system. In coming time, the marks (life style and standard and the area they residing) easily recognizing Dalit and Adivashi should be vanished and everyone should get equal social and political status and good income source. I am sure that when these reserved people will come at par of upper class then they themselves will throw the support of reservation. Each and every individuals and communities progress is the progress of our country.